

EUPHEMISMS AS AN OBJECT OF STUDY IN LINGUISTICS

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Abstract: *Euphemisms are classified into pure and contextual euphemisms. The function of pure euphemisms is directly derived from their own meanings. This article is devoted to the euphemisms as an object of study in linguistics.*

Key words: *euphemisms, contextual euphemisms, linguistics.*

The phenomenon of Euphemia and the definition of euphemism in linguistic literature. There are several definitions of the concept of "euphemism" in linguistic literature. They reflect the various functions of this phenomenon. The problem of Euphemia in linguistic literature has been repeatedly considered in the materials of various languages in the works of domestic and foreign linguists.

Euphemia tools for the English language are a field of traditional research from the 60s of the 20th century. At this stage, collected lexical materials are ordered and presented in special dictionaries in English lexicography euphemisms are also included in annotated dictionaries.

In Russian linguistics, the problems of Euphemia were not sufficiently noticed for a long time due to the Soviet belief that "euphemisms characteristic of the socialist era are exposed and their preference for direct expressions". Euphemisms are not included in explanatory dictionaries of the Russian language, there are no special dictionaries of this genre. V.G. Belinsky's view that "it is necessary to use such a word so that no other word can be found to replace it"¹ is also related to the ethical-aesthetic demand norm of euphemic speech.

The ethical-aesthetic requirement norm of euphemic speech is the art of maximizing the use of this colorful and inexhaustible wealth of euphemic synonyms in a certain space and time for a certain purpose².

It should be noted that euphemic means do not serve only for the positivity, sophistication of concepts that are not intended to be said openly. Because even when logically negative concepts are euphemized, the essence remains. But this process is still guided by the aesthetic requirement norm of the application of euphemia.

¹ Белинский В.Г. Избранные сочинения. В 3-х томах. Т. II. –Москва, 1948. – С.694.

² Маматов А.Э. Проблемы лексико-фразеологической нормы в современном узбекском литературном языке: Автороф. дис...доктора филол. наук. –Ташкент, 1991. – С 20.

The idea that "a language will not have two similar words that exactly represent a single concept, equal to each other," reiterates the fact that euphemic synonyms cannot be applied indifferently, they have their own subtle stylistic coloring, the norm of application¹.

To more accurately understand the nature of euphemism, the studied definitions were analyzed and divided into three large groups. The criterion was the types of functions performed by euphemism, reflected in the definitions under consideration.

The first group includes definitions in which the only function of euphemism is considered to be the mitigation of rude and unpleasant things: Fowler argues that "euphemism is a soft, vague or periphrastic expression to replace coarse clarity or unpleasant reality".

Euphemisms are classified into pure and contextual euphemisms. The function of pure euphemisms is directly derived from their own meanings. Contextual (textual) euphemisms are a genre or colloquial text with the aim of enriching the expression of thought (a fragment of speech that, in terms of content, has completeness, allows you to define the meanings of words or phrases in its composition. The words (phrases) contained in such a fragment of speech will be characteristic of one that acts as an envelope for the other.

S. Cain, on the other hand, believes that "euphemism is an indirect, or milder, term for a way to replace an unpleasant, offensive, or frightening word".

I. R. Galperin comments that "euphemism is a word or phrase used to replace an unpleasant word or phrase with a relatively more acceptable one"².

A. Spears rates "euphemism - replacing coarse expression with softer and more acceptable".

In addition to the main function of mitigation, the definitions of the second Group note the importance of social motives:

E. According to Partridge, euphemisms are phrases that are "designed to minimize the unpleasant impression of the listener, or the possible unpleasant consequences for the speaker if the latter wants to make a positive impression".

A. Katsev argues that "euphemisms are phrases that contribute to the indirect substitute mitigation effect of monstrous, shameful, or strange names that lead to life for moral or religious reasons"³.

¹ Белинский В.Г. Избранные сочинения. В 3-х томах. Т. II. –Москва, 1988. –С.84.

² Галперин И.Р. Очерки по стилистике английского языка. – Москва: Лит. на иностр. языков, 1958. –С 72; Исматуллаев Н. Эвфемизмы в современном узбекском языке: Автореф. дис... канд. филол. наук. – Ташкент, 1983. -С.18

³ Кацев А.М. Эвфемизмы в современном английском языке. – Ленинград: Наука, 1997. – 65 с.

S. Allan et al. Barridge believes it is "a phrase used by a speaker, audience member, or third party as an alternative to a phrase that is not preferred so as not to lose its meaning".

L. Krysin says that "euphemistic substitution is used to avoid communicative conflicts and failures, not to create a feeling of communicative discomfort in the interlocutor."

E. Tyurina says that "euphemisms are soft and permissive, reclamation-allegorical, and sometimes more acceptable words or phrases for some reason or another, which are used instead of thematic stigma or socially incorrect antecedents".

In the definitions included in the third group, one of the main ones is the function of masking reality:

J. According to Lawrence, "euphemism is (for various reasons) a form of word that softens an idea or expresses it with veils or more respect. In addition, this softening is sometimes only visible¹".

J. Niman, etc. Silver says "euphemization is the use of a term that is not absorbed or pleasant instead of direct, offensive in hiding the truth".

Summing up all of the above, we can conclude that euphemism performs three functions:

1. Soften rude and unpleasant things for the speaker;

In this case, the speaker evaluates the topic of speech in such a way that its direct designation is recognized by him as rudeness, accuracy, indecency.

2. Soften rude and unpleasant things for the interlocutor;

This dependence of the use of euphemism on context and speech conditions manifests itself as the social conditioning of the idea that euphemism can be.

3. Hiding the truth;

At the same time, the speaker chooses such notes, which not only soften some inappropriate words or phrases, but also mask, hide the essence of the phenomenon.

In our opinion, in the definition of euphemism, all its functions must be taken into account. That is, a new improved definition can be given that reflects the broad understanding of Euphemia adopted in this work:

Euphemism is a phrase used in order to replace any illegal or inappropriate word or phrase with a direct one, to avoid the direct naming of anything that causes negative emotions in the speaker and interlocutor, as well as to hide some facts of reality.

¹ Лоуренс Д. Порнография и непристойности. – Москва: Азбуковник, 2003. 189 с.

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